

A STUDY ON BEST FEATURES OF WOOD LAND FOOTWEAR AND BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF ITS USERS

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Abstract:

Conducting study on buying behavior is the attempt to understand and predict human action in the buying role. It has assumed growing importance under customer-oriented marketing planning and management. Buyers for many products and growth of consumerism have created special interest in buyer behavior in the market place. Customer perceptions are based on feelings. Customer perception encompasses a customer's impression, awareness and/or consciousness about a company or its offerings. Customer perception is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experiences and other channels. A Customer perception measurement is an important tool used by companies that expresses how well the companies are satisfying customers and the best features which are attracted by its customers. In order to find the best features of Wood Land footwear and the factors influencing Wood Land footwear Users' buying behavior this study deals with the same.

Key Words: Buying Behavior, Footwear, Perception, Social Factors, Psychological Factors & Personal Factors

1. Introduction:

For millions of years, the human foot has been either bare or covered with very simple footwear to protect the bottoms of the feet. These foot coverings were adequate to protect the bottom of the foot from sharp rocks and rough terrain. The first form of footwear consisted of a simple piece of plaited grass or rawhide which was strapped to the feet. The foot contains more bone than any other single part of the body. Though it has evolved over hundreds of years in relation to vastly varied terrain and climate condition, the foot is still vulnerable to environmental hazards such as sharp rocks and hot ground against which footwear can protect. Traditionally, footwear have been made from leather, wood or canvas, but are increasingly made from rubber, plastics and other petrochemical-derived materials. With the advent of today's modern footwear came a whole array of foot problems complete with companies that made therapeutic devices and professionals to treat such conditions. Many companies and individuals have benefited as the footwear business and those products and services connected with the epidemic of foot problems in big business. Our footwear fashions of today are, for the most part, modernized adaptations of past styles. Customer perception is the way that customers usually view or feel about certain services and products. It can also be related to customer satisfaction which is the expectation of the customer towards the product [1]. When customer's perceptions about Wood Land footwear are good, they will continue purchasing footwear from this company. These customers also will avoid spreading disappointing experiences to others. Customers those are satisfied with Wood Land footwear have an overall good perception on that product. Knowledge of customer perception and attitudes about Wood Land footwear will greatly enhance the opportunity to make better business decisions.

2. Statement of the Problem:

Customer perception describes how customer's view or understand a company and its product. Nowadays, there are many brands of footwear available in Krishnagiri district. Recently, Wood Land footwear is the popular brand and it provides quality

footwear at affordable prices to the customer. Though there exist many advantages in customer perception, some negative aspects also prevails. Some customers are unaware about Wood Land footwear. Some Wood Land footwear user' are not having brand sticking tendency. Some customers may be attracted by the features of other brand. To solve these problems the following questions should be answered.

1. What are all the factors influencing the Wood Land footwear users' buying behaviour?
4. What are the best features which are attracted by Wood Land footwear users?

3. Review of Literature:

Review of various studies provides the sufficient background to proceed the present study.

Ron Ruggless (2001) finds that the customer in such a manner that he becomes loyal to the company and is unlikely to switch to the competitors. As the market-place becomes more and more competitive and the environment, to retain the customers, it is essential that organizations focus on customer's notice and understand [2].

Jeannie Walters (2003) describes that customer perception is no different. Each person within the organisations has a role to play. There are specific time sensitive challenges and objectives tied to each person's livelihood. It becomes the individual's sole responsibility to focus on reaching those goals [3].

According to Chris Blank, (2004) customer perception theory attempts to explain customer behaviour by analysing motivations for buying- or not buying- particular items. Customer perception applies the concept of sensory perception of marketing and advertising. Just as sensory perception relates to how humans perceive and process sensory stimuli through their five senses, customer perception pertain to how individuals form opinion about companies and the merchandise they offer through the purchases they make. Merchants apply customer perception theory to determine how their customer's perceive them [4].

Dagmar Recklies (2005) concluded that customer perception can be understood as to how customers feel about a product, service or brand and whether their perceived total investments with live up to their expectations [5].

Mercuri Urval's (2006) finds from his study customer perception analysis is a value-chain assessment methodology that gives you a better understanding of your interaction with customers [6].

Russell-Bennett, McColl-Kennedy and Coote (2006) finds from his study customer's involvement is also important as when buyer consider the product important and invests time to seek information then it ultimately enhances the perception level [7].

According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2008) customer perception may be defined as the perception that customers understand in searching for, purchasing, using,evaluating and disposing of products, services and ideas which they expect will satisfy their needs [8].

Janneke Blijlevens, Marielle E.H.Creusen and Jan P.L.Schoormans (2009) say that the appearance attributes of designed products noted in the literature often reflect what designers themselves perceive in a product design. This present research, however provides knowledge on how customer's perceive product appearance by identifying appearance attributes that customers use to distinguish the appearances of durable products. Descriptions of appearance were generated by customers in a free categorization task. The appearance attributes identified in this research provides knowledge of what customers see in durable product acceptance. Knowledge of what

appearance attributes are perceived by customers in a product design can help a designer to communicate certain pre-specified meanings in a product [9].

4. Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of this study:

1. To study the factors influencing Wood Land footwear user's buying behaviour.
2. To find out the best attractive features of Wood Land footwear.

5. Methodology and Tools:

This study is an empirical research. The primary data were collected by using interview schedule. Survey method is adopted for this study. Data were collected directly from the sample respondents by interviewing them personally.

6. Sampling Design:

The sample respondents should be the representatives of the population. In such a way the sample respondents are selected by using non-probability convenience sampling method. The Krishnagiri district was selected for this study. By considering the time, the sample size of 50 respondents was selected by using the above sampling design.

7. Period of the Study:

The study is conducted during the year 2015.

8. Limitation of the Study:

The study has certain limitations

1. As the time and resources are limited, all the Wood Land footwear users in Krishnagiri district could not be studied for this research purpose.
2. The area of the study is limited in Krishnagiri district only, so that result may not be true to other geographical regions.
3. It has been found that many of the respondents have not come forward to express their opinion frankly. Because of the above limitations, it may not reveal the real position about the customer perception towards Wood Land footwear.

9. Findings:

9 (a) The Factors Influencing Customer's Buying Behaviour:

The success or failure in marketing depends upon the individuals' reactions, expressed in the form of buying pattern. The buyer is subject to many influences before the actual purchase. The buyer behaviour has many approaches, the social the psychological and the personal etc. The social factors include friends, family members, neighbours, co-staff, religious, professional and aspiration group persons. The psychological factors include motivation, perception, learning and attitudes. The personal factors include age, occupation, income and life style.

The buying behaviour will differ from person to person. The buyer is considered as a black box, because his mind cannot be imagined, as to his buying decision. The buying decision depends on his attitude, preferences, perception, feelings etc. factors influencing the customer behaviour are internal-needs, motives, perception and attitude as well as external family, social groups, culture, economics business influences etc.

In order to find the buying behaviour of Wood Land footwear users seventeen questions have been asked. These seventeen questions have been categorized into three parts. The first six questions related to psychological factors and the remaining five questions related to personal factor. To analyse the perception of sample respondents, Likert's 2-point scaling technique has been (yes/no). It has been categorized as factors influencing and not influencing the Wood Land footwear users buying behavior. If a respondent agrees a statement he will score 2 points. Else his score will be 1. As per this calculation, a respondent can score maximum 12 (6×2) and minimum (6×1) from first

two category and for the last factor, a respondent can score maximum 10 (5×2) and minimum 5 (5×1). After providing the points for all questions, each category has been totaled separately. The respondent who scores upto 8 in first two categories are considered as that Wood Land footwear user has not been influenced by such factors. If the total score exceeds 8 in first two categories then it is considered as that respondent has been influenced by such factor. He last category explains that the respondent who scores up to 7 is considered as that Wood Land footwear users has not been influenced by such factor. If the total score exceeds 7, then it is considered as that respondent has been influenced by such factor. As per this calculation the following results are obtained.

Table 1
Buying Behaviour Influenced By Social Factors

S.No	Effect of Social Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Influenced	40	80%
2	Not influenced	10	20%
	Total	50	100%

CHART 1
SAMPLE RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR
BUYING BEHAVIOUR INFLUENCED BY SOCIAL
FACTORS

Table 1 and Chart 1 shows that out of 50 (100%) sample respondents 40 (80%) respondents have influenced by the social factors. The remaining 10 (20%) respondents have not influenced by the social factors.

Table 2
Buying Behaviour Influenced By Psychological Factors

S.No	Effect of Psychological Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Influenced	39	78%
2	Not influenced	11	22%
	Total	50	100%

Chart 2
Buying Behaviour Influenced By Psychological Factors

Table 2 and Chart 2 shows that out of 50 (100%) sample respondents 39 (78%) respondents have influenced by the psychological factors. The remaining 11 (22%) respondents have not influenced by the psychological factors.

Table 3
Buying Behaviour Influenced By Personal Factors

S.No	Effect of Personal Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Influenced	41	82%
2	Not influenced	09	18%
	Total	50	100%

Chart 3
Buying Behaviour Influenced By Personal Factors

Table 3 and Chart 3 shows that out of 50 (100%) sample respondents 41 (82%) respondents have influenced by the personal factors. The remaining 9 (18%) respondents have not influenced by the personal factors.

9 (b) Attractive Features:

In order to find the attractive features of Wood Land footwear, this study focuses on the best features of Wood Land footwear which are attracted by Wood Land footwear users. The Wood Land footwear users may be attracted by some features such as low price, high quality, allowing discount, availability, very stylish, various collection, durability, various colours available, grip and sizes to all age group. In order to find the degree in which the features of Wood Land footwear attract the Wood Land users, the respondents are asked to assign the rank for the features of Wood Land footwear. After that by using weighted average technique the score was given to each and every features of Wood Land footwear. Finally the attractive feature, which scores the more points, got the first rank. Then the feature, which scores next to the high score, got the second rank. Likewise these best attractive features are assigned by the rank. The Table 4 shows the points scored by each and every feature of Wood Land footwear attracted by Wood Land footwear users.

Table 4
Best Attractive Features Wood Land Footwear: Ranking Analysis

Features/Rank	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	TOTAL
Low price	80 (08)	54 (06)	72 (09)	56 (08)	18 (03)	35 (07)	08 (02)	09 (03)	04 (02)	02 (02)	338 (50)
High quality	90 (09)	63 (07)	40 (05)	70 (10)	42 (07)	20 (04)	08 (02)	00 (00)	02 (01)	05 (05)	340 (50)
Allowing discount	50 (05)	36 (04)	32 (04)	14 (02)	06 (01)	25 (05)	36 (09)	12 (04)	14 (07)	09 (09)	234 (50)
Availability	30 (03)	09 (01)	48 (06)	21 (03)	12 (02)	30 (06)	28 (07)	24 (08)	20 (10)	04 (04)	226 (50)
Very stylish	60 (06)	27 (03)	48 (06)	35 (05)	18 (03)	25 (05)	16 (04)	18 (06)	10 (05)	07 (07)	264 (50)
Various collection	70 (07)	54 (06)	08 (01)	35 (05)	36 (06)	30 (06)	00 (00)	21 (07)	14 (07)	05 (05)	273 (50)
Durability	00 (00)	63 (07)	16 (02)	28 (04)	36 (06)	20 (04)	12 (03)	24 (08)	16 (08)	08 (08)	223 (50)
Various colours available	50 (05)	27 (03)	32 (04)	21 (03)	48 (08)	20 (04)	40 (10)	15 (05)	10 (05)	03 (03)	266 (50)
Grip	60 (06)	99 (11)	56 (07)	28 (04)	42 (07)	15 (03)	16 (04)	12 (04)	02 (01)	03 (03)	333 (50)
Sizes to all age group	10 (01)	18 (02)	48 (06)	42 (06)	42 (07)	30 (06)	36 (09)	15 (05)	08 (04)	04 (04)	253 (50)

(Figures in the cells denote scores. Figures in the parenthesis denotes number of respondents)

Table 4 and Chart 4 was analysed by using the weighted average technique, the rank was assigned as follows.

1. High quality
2. Low price
3. Grip
4. Various collections
5. Various colours available
6. Very stylish
7. Sizes to all age group
8. Allowing discount
9. Availability
10. Durability

From the above analysis it can be concluded that, the best attractive feature of Wood Land footwear is 'High Quality'. Because it scores more points (340). The second attractive feature is 'Low Price'. It scores 338 points. The customers are quickly attracted by the low price footwear when compared to high price. The third attractive feature is 'Grip'. It scores 333 points. The customers thought that the Wood Land footwear provide much grip while walking. The fourth attractive feature is 'Various Collections'. It scores 273 points. The customers like to wear various collections of footwear according to their lifestyle. The fifth attractive feature is 'Various Colours available'. It scores 266 points. The customers are expected that various colours are available in Wood Land footwear. The sixth attractive feature is 'Very Stylish'. It scores 264 points. Some customers are very interested to wear stylish footwear. The seventh attractive feature is 'Sizes to all age group'. It scores 253 points. The customers give importance to the sizes of footwear to all age group. The eighth attractive feature is

'Allowing Discount'. It scores 234 points. Some customers are satisfied with discount allowed by Wood Land footwear. The ninth attractive feature is 'Availability'. It scores 226 points. The last and tenth attractive feature is 'Durability'. It scores 223 points.

10. Summary:

The study shows that out of 50 (100%) sample respondents 40 (80%) respondents have influenced by the social factors. They like to get information from the society about the footwear and they like to follow the purchasing decisions which are made by their aspiration group persons. They refer the ideas given by friends, advertisements, relatives and they seek sales representatives' advice to take decision to buy particular brand of footwear. They like to maintain their vanity in this society by spending some expenses and enrich their status by purchasing luxury footwear. Out of 50 (100%) sample respondents 10 (20%) respondents have not influenced by the social factors. They don't like to gather information from others. They never consider others while making a purchase. As for as they are considered their own decision are good for them.

From this study it can be know that 39 (78%) respondents have influenced by the psychological factors. While making purchase they analyse all the details of different footwear. Their purchase decisions are based on their own tendency towards the footwear. They purchase footwear on the basis of prompt decision taken by them. Mostly they purchase footwear as a result of their mental forces. The remaining 11 (22%) respondents have not influenced by the psychological factors. Even though they like to purchase footwear they will not purchase that footwear by taking prompt decision. They have not considered their past learning experiences; they are not taking purchase decision according to their own tendency towards the footwear.

The study shows that 41 (82%) respondents have influenced by the personal factors. While making a purchase they compare the price of the footwear with their income level. They expect that the footwear should be match with their own life style. They consider their occupation and age while making a purchase decision. They consider that whether they can maintain the footwear properly or not. The remaining 9 (18%) respondents have not influenced by the personal factors. While making a purchase they never consider the price of the footwear. They have not expected that the footwear should be match with their own life style. They never consider that whether they can maintain the footwear properly or not. They also not consider the occupation and their age while purchasing the footwear. From this study it is found that the Wood Land footwear users are mostly attracted by its 'High Quality'. After that they are attracted by its 'Low Price'. The third best factor of the Wood Land footwear is 'The Grip' of the footwear. Then the footwear users are giving preference to the following features one by one. They are 'Various Collection', 'Various colours available', 'Very stylish', 'Sizes to all age group', 'Allowing Discount', 'Availability' and 'Durability'.

11. Suggestion and Recommendations:

On the basis of the findings of the study, it is suggested to implement the following suggestion and recommendations to improve the Wood Land footwear in the entire manner.

1. This study shows that the best features of Wood Land footwear are high quality, low price and sufficient grip. So the company should try to keep up the quality and the price in the same level. While manufacturing the footwear more concentration should be given to grip of the footwear.
2. The company may provide after sale service to retain their customers.
3. Introduction of cash back offer would attract new customers.

4. Providing warranty for footwear will create good image about Wood Land footwear in the minds of public.

These are all the suggestions and recommendations provided by the customers to improve the Wood Land footwear.

12. Conclusion:

Customer behavior and perception plays a major role in marketing. This study reveals the customer behavior and customer perception towards Wood Land footwear in Krishnagiri district. It can be known from this study once the customers are fixed with the product they cannot get back to the other one. Most of the respondents are highly aware about the Wood Land footwear. Only a few number of respondents are feel that the Wood Land footwear has giving some problems. If this company satisfy those people it can be firmly say that the Wood Land footwear will be the popular brand of all other brands.

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